

CAST IRON: A NATURAL METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The deformation micromechanics of flake and spheroidal graphitic cast iron have been studied using Raman spectroscopy. It has been found that the Raman peak position shifted to a lower wavenumber upon application of a tensile strain, and to a higher wavenumber upon application of a compressive strain. The elastic properties of cast iron have been investigated using various theoretical models. It has been shown for flake graphite that the elastic modulus and level of graphite stress at 1% strain is in close agreement to the models for disk-shaped inclusions, and to the models for spherical inclusions for spheroidal iron. Raman spectroscopy can follow the immediate elastic recovery of the cast iron and can pinpoint the onset of permanent plastic deformation by comparing the position of the Raman peak before and immediately after unloading.

KEYWORDS: Micromechanics, Cast Iron, Raman Spectroscopy, Graphite.

INTRODUCTION

Cast iron is essentially an iron-carbon-silicon alloy containing other elements such as manganese, sulphur and phosphorus, which modify the structure and properties of the resulting alloy. The carbon in excess of its solubility in solid iron is present as graphite in grey cast irons and as Fe₃C (cementite) in white cast irons. The graphite in spheroidal irons occurs as finely dispersed spheroids and in flake irons as interconnected graphite flakes. Cast iron is being treated as a composite in this study where the graphite flakes are modelled as a disk-shaped reinforcement and the graphite spheroids as spherical-shaped reinforcement. Cast iron samples have been studied, [1] which show a sharp Raman band at 1580cm⁻¹, weak bands at around 1300 cm⁻¹ and 1620cm⁻¹ and a strong band around 1350cm⁻¹. The applicability of the Raman technique to the study of iron and steel has been discussed by Sato [2]. The technique has been used for the analysis of corrosion products and slags. For example, first order Raman bands in the range 298-663 cm⁻¹ have been found for a variety of iron oxides such as α-FeOOH and FeO. In this study, samples of cast iron have been deformed and Raman spectroscopy used to follow the stress-induced carbon bandshift.

Modelling Elastic Properties of Cast Iron

As with fibre-reinforced, particulate composite properties depend on the relative amounts and properties of the individual constituents. In cast irons, the graphite phase is softer and less stiff than the iron matrix and its morphology determines properties such as the strength and ductility of the iron. Graphite particle shape affects the properties of cast irons both physical and mechanical, as does the volume fraction of the graphite.

Voigt Model

This model is most useful for the case of a normal stress being applied parallel to the fibre axis in a fibre reinforced composite [3].

$$E_c = (1 - V_p)E_m + V_pE_p \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts c, p and m refer to the composite, graphite particles and matrix respectively, E = Young's modulus and V = volume fraction.

Reuss Model

The uniform stress boundary is obtained by considering a stress applied perpendicular to the fibre axis in the so that the composite strains can be expressed in terms of the applied stress [3], to give:

$$E_c = \left[\frac{V_p}{E_p} + \frac{(1 - V_p)}{E_m} \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Hashin Model

Hashin, [4] gave solutions for the elastic moduli of a 2-phase solid containing a random distribution of spherical particles by considering the changes in strain energy in a loaded homogeneous body caused by the insertion of inhomogeneities. It is assumed that the particles are spherical and that the action of the 2-phase material on any one particle is transmitted through a spherical shell lying wholly in the matrix. The upper and lower bounds for the bulk and shear moduli are calculated using the principle of minimum strain energy and is approximated by:

$$K_c = K_m \left[1 - \frac{3(1 - \nu_m)(1 - K_p / K_m)}{2(1 - 2\nu_m) + (1 + \nu_m) K_p / K_m} V_p \right] \quad (3)$$

$$G_c = G_m \left[1 - \frac{15(1 - \nu_m)(1 - G_p / G_m)}{(7 - 5\nu_m) + 2(4 - 5\nu_m) G_p / G_m} V_p \right] \quad (4)$$

Where K_c and G_c are the bulk and shear moduli of the composite respectively and ν_m is the Poisson's ratio of the matrix. To calculate the Young's modulus of spherical-shaped particles, the eqns (3) and (4) and the standard relationship between isotropic elastic constants can be used:

$$E_c = \frac{9K_c G_c}{(3K_c + G_c)} \quad (5)$$

Wu Model

Wu [5] showed that the elastic moduli of a 2-phase solid are more strongly affected by disk shaped particles than by spherical particles. To simplify the solution some assumptions must be made. Wu used the strain field theory about an ellipsoidal inclusion given by Eshelby [3]. Wu's equations are simplified by assuming that the composite, the matrix and the inclusions all have a Poissons ratio of 0.2 giving:

$$E_c = E_m \left[\frac{2 - (1 - E_p / E_m) V_p}{2 - (1 - E_m / E_p) V_p} \right] \quad (6)$$

Rossi Model

Rossi, [6] derived expressions for the elastic moduli of a 2-phase solid with small concentrations of disk-shaped particles of the form:

$$E_c = E_m (1 - S V_p) \quad (7)$$

where S is a stress concentration factor and is determined by the axial ratio of the disk-shaped particle and by the ratio of E_p/E_m .

Halpin-Tsai Model

A model has been suggested by Halpin and Tsai, [7] which is not based on exact elasticity theory but broadly takes into account enhanced inclusion loading, relative to the equal stress assumption:

$$E_c = \frac{E_m (1 - \xi \eta V_p)}{(1 - \eta V_p)} \quad \text{where } \eta = \frac{\left(\frac{E_p}{E_m} - 1 \right)}{\left(\frac{E_p}{E_m} + \xi \right)} \quad (8)$$

The value of ξ is taken as an adjustable dimension parameter but its magnitude is generally of the order of unity.

EXPERIMENTAL

The grade Gr220 flake cast iron was supplied by Forrest & Sym Foundry, Manchester. Typical microadditions to flake and spheroidal cast irons are carbon, silicon, manganese, sulphur and phosphorus with spheroidal iron also having magnesium as a spheroidiser. The amount of sulphur and phosphorous must be low in spheroidal irons but not in flake irons, [8]. The cast iron was cut into beams ($1 \times 10 \times 60$ mm) then ground and polished. The resistance strain gauge was attached onto the top surface of the beam using a cyanoacrylate adhesive. The beam samples were inserted into a four-point bending rig which was attached to the stage of the optical microscope. Strain was applied successively to the beam, as determined by the resistance sensitive strain gauge. The spectra were obtained using a Renishaw 1000 Raman system using the 632.8nm red line of a 25mW He-Ne laser. The intensity of the laser beam on the sample surface using a $\times 50$ microscope objective lens was about 1.3mW. The peak values were derived by using Lorentzian routines fitted to the raw data obtained from the CCD detector. Tensile testing of the cast iron was carried out on an Instron 1185 tensile testing machine using a Hounsfield extensometer with a gauge length of 25mm. Five dumbbell specimens of cast iron were machined from the same section of iron used for the Raman experiments and had an average diameter of 7.93 ± 0.2 mm. The configuration of the beams under tensile and compressive loading can be seen in fig 1.

Figure 1 Composite beams under (a) tensile and (a) compressive loading.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microscopy of Samples

A polished sample of flake cast iron was etched for 10 seconds in 2% Nital and examined using optical microscopy. Fig 2(a) shows the alternating layers of the cementite and ferrite of the pearlitic matrix and the random orientation of the graphite flakes. Fig 2(b) shows an optical micrograph of polished spheroidal iron (grade Gr500-7) photographed under polarised light. It can be seen that the graphite crystallites radiate from a common centre.

Figure 2 Optical Micrographs of (a) graphite flake and (b) graphite nodules

Tensile testing

Table 1 shows a summary of the elastic modulus obtained for the flake and spheroidal cast iron samples compared with literature values. The elastic modulus (82.1GPa) obtained from tensile testing of flake iron was lower than the literature value of 120GPa [8]. The reason for this difference could be traced possibly to defects present in the material. The elastic modulus obtained for spheroidal iron was 180.7GPa which is slightly higher than the literature value of 176GPa.

Cast Iron	Volume Fraction of Graphite (%)	Experimental Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Literature [5] Elastic Modulus (GPa)
Flake Graphite	0.11	82.1 ± 7.2	120
Spheroidal Graphite	0.09	180.7 ± 9.5	176

Table 1 Tensile test results for flake and spheroidal cast iron

Raman Spectroscopy

Fig 3 shows the Raman spectrum of a graphite flake and graphite nodule in the range $1000\text{-}3000\text{cm}^{-1}$. A sharp peak is seen at 1582cm^{-1} which is characteristic of graphite structures [9]. A band is seen at 1335cm^{-1} which has been attributed to the breakdown of translational symmetry produced by the microcrystalline structure [10]. In the undeformed specimens of flake and spheroidal cast irons the peak position of the second order Raman band is about 2673cm^{-1} .

Figure 3 Raman Spectrum of a graphite flake and a graphite spheroid in cast iron

This is higher than the second order Raman band position for a carbon fibre in air or highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (about 2660cm^{-1}) and could indicate residual compressive stresses in the graphite flakes or nodules or be due to structural imperfections. The 2673cm^{-1} band is asymmetric and examination reveals that it could be two bands. Fitting for two bands finds a lower frequency component at 2654cm^{-1} and a higher frequency component at 2689cm^{-1} . The origin of these two bands is unclear but it may be that the 1335cm^{-1} peak is actually a doublet. The asymmetrical nature of this Raman band is not seen in other carbon materials so will be investigated further.

Strain Dependence of the 2674cm^{-1} Raman Band for Flake and Spheroidal Cast Iron

	Tension ($\text{cm}^{-1} / \%$)	Compression ($\text{cm}^{-1} / \%$)
Flake Iron	-1.5 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.5
Spheroidal iron	-2.6 ± 0.4	1.3 ± 0.6

Table 2. Summary of Raman bandshift rates for flake and spheroidal cast iron. Raman spectra are particularly sensitive to specific aspects of the lowering of crystalline ordering such as the in-plane crystalline size, the onset of three-dimensional ordering and the establishment of long-range three-dimensional ordering [11]. Deformation of the graphite flakes induces disorder in the graphite lattice causing the Raman bands to broaden and the I_D/I_G ratio to decrease. From figs 4 and 5 it can be seen that the 2674cm^{-1} Raman band shifts to a lower wavenumber upon the application of a tensile strain and to a higher wavenumber with applied compressive strain. A summary of the Raman bandshift rates is shown in table 2.

Figure 4 Variation of the 2674cm^{-1} Raman peak position with applied tensile strain.

Figure 5 Variation of the 2674cm^{-1} Raman peak position with applied tensile strain

For general purpose flake cast irons, the onset of plastic deformation is at about 0.2-0.3% strain while for spheroidal irons, the onset is at about 0.5-0.6%, [12]. Some of the plots of the variation of Raman peak position with strain showed a ‘dip’ in the curve as seen in figs 4 and 5. The level of strain at which the ‘dip’ occurred was about 0.15-0.25% for flake iron. This is lower than the literature value for yield but is in agreement with the stress-strain data obtained for the Gr220 samples. In the spheroidal samples, the ‘dip’ occurred at about 0.3-0.4% strain which again is slightly lower than the literature value. It can be seen that there is less scatter in the data before the ‘dip’ than after it. This could indicate that damage is occurring in the graphite with increasing strain. Raman spectroscopy could be a useful tool to indicate the strain level in the graphite flake both as the load is applied to the cast iron and also pre- and post-yield.

Unloading of Flake and Graphite Cast iron

Raman spectra was also taken immediately after unloading and can be seen as the black-filled circle on figs 4 and 5. The level of strain reached at the onset of plastic deformation is indicated by the position of the black data point after unloading. For the flake iron samples, the unloading point was at about 0.12% strain which is lower than the literature value but is linked to the lower Young’s modulus found in the tensile test results. The unloading point for the spheroidal iron samples was at about 0.5% strain which is in agreement with the literature value. The unloading point in this case was higher than the corresponding ‘dip’ which could be linked to the slightly greater value for Young’s modulus achieved in the tensile tests than is quoted in literature. Raman spectroscopy can follow the immediate elastic recovery of the cast iron and can pinpoint the onset of permanent plastic deformation by comparing the position of the Raman peak before and immediately after unloading.

Modelling of the Elastic Properties of Cast Iron

The elastic properties of a composite material depend on the properties of the constituent phases and their geometry, as expressed by their relative amount and morphology. The theoretical

models of Voigt, Halpin-Tsai, Hashin, Rossi, Wu and Reuss have been used to estimate the elastic modulus of cast iron which has been modelled as a two-phase composite comprising of randomly oriented graphite particles embedded in an isotropic iron matrix. The model derived by Rossi, [6] for disk-shaped particles uses a stress concentration factor, S which has been calculated to be 4.8. Graphite flakes are nearly single crystals whereas graphite spheroids are polycrystalline giving different graphite elastic modulus. However, because of the very large difference between the graphite and iron matrix modulus, it is not believed that a significant error is introduced if both spheroids and flakes are assumed to have the same modulus. The values for bulk and shear moduli and Poisson's ratio are taken from Speich et al.[13] and used in eqn (10) to calculate the elastic modulus for the cast iron matrix and graphite as shown in table 3. Using these values and eqns (1) to (8) the variation of Young's modulus, E_c , with graphite content is plotted for the Voigt, Reuss, Hashin, Wu, Rossi and Halpen-Tsai models as shown in fig 6.

	Poisson's ratio, ν_M	K (GPa)	G (GPa)	E (GPa)
Graphite inclusions	0.2	6.7	3.3	8.5
Iron matrix	0.2	162.3	81.3	209

Table 3 Values for bulk, shear and elastic modulus for the iron matrix and graphite particles [13]

The value of Young's modulus taken from the literature and obtained from tensile testing are also plotted for comparison in fig 6. The modulus decreases with increasing graphite content for all the models as the graphite modulus is much lower than the matrix modulus. The Voigt model holds good for inclusions long enough for the equal strain assumptions to apply and deviations are expected as a result of stresses which arise when the Poisson's ratios are not equal. Both the Voigt and Reuss models can only approximate the modulus as the real composite is neither equally stressed or equally strained.

Figure 6 Variation of Young's modulus with graphite content for various theoretical models

Table 4 shows the calculated values of Young's modulus for various theoretical models. In comparing the experimental and literature values for the Young's modulus of flake iron with the theoretical models, it can be seen that the values lie closest to the predictions of Wu and Rossi. These models are based on disk-shaped inclusions which reflects the flake graphite shape in the Gr220 samples.

Theoretical Models	Elastic Modulus (GPa) Flake Iron	Elastic Modulus (GPa) Spheroidal Iron
Voigt	186.7	191.0
Reuss	57.8	66.9
Wu	85.7	97.0
Hashin	166.2	174.3
Halpin-Tsai	170.2	177.0
Rossi	97.6	118.7
Literature Value	120.0	179.9
Experimental Value	82.1 ± 7.2	180.7 ± 9.5

Table 4 Values of elastic modulus from the theoretical models for flake and spheroidal cast iron
The literature and experimentally measured values for the Young's modulus of spheroidal iron are in close agreement with the predicted values of Hashin and Halpin-Tsai. The Hashin model is based on a random distribution of spherical-shaped particles reflecting the situation for the spherulitic iron.

Particle Stress

Young, [11] found that the values of Raman shift per unit strain for PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibres when plotted directly as a function of fibre modulus fall approximately on a straight line. The slope of $1.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{GPa}$ for this plot was used as an universal calibration figure to calculate the stress for flake and spheroidal cast iron measured during the deformation experiments. The strain induced Raman bandshift per percentage strain is: $d\Delta\nu/d\varepsilon$, ($\text{cm}^{-1} / \%$), and the universal calibration is: $d\Delta\nu/d\sigma = 1.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{GPa}$. where $\sigma = \text{stress}$ and $\varepsilon = \text{strain}$. Assuming an uniform stress situation in the cast iron and using the linear relationship for Young's modulus, $d\sigma = E.d\varepsilon$, at 1% strain the stress in the graphite is $(d\Delta\nu / d\varepsilon)/1.6 \text{ GPa}$. Using eqns (1) to (8) the value of graphite stress at 1% strain was calculated for flake and spheroidal irons. These were plotted as a function of graphite content along with the predicted values of stress calculated using the theoretical models at an applied strain of 1% and using the relationship $E = \sigma/\varepsilon$ The value E was taken from the theoretical models calculations as summarised in table 4.

Figure 7 Variation of stress at 1% strain with increasing graphite content for various theoretical models

The variation of stress at 1% strain with increasing graphite content is shown in fig 7. It can be seen that the experimental value of stress taken for flake iron falls between the values predicted by Rossi and Wu similar to the elastic modulus positions shown in fig 6. The experimental stress calculated for spheroidal iron lies closest to the stress predicted by the Hashin model for spherical inclusions.

CONCLUSIONS

The structure / property relationships of flake and spheroidal cast iron has been investigated. Raman spectroscopy has been used to characterise the spectrum arising from the vibrational modes of the cast iron where the graphite flakes and nodules are modelled as inclusions in an iron matrix. The samples were deformed and the Raman peak shift rate used to follow the transfer of stress or strain from the matrix to the reinforcing phase. For a simple 2-phase composite under a given load, a certain proportion of that load will be carried by the reinforcement and the remainder by the matrix. The proportion of load carried by the reinforcement depends upon the volume fraction, shape and orientation of the reinforcement and on the elastic properties of both constituents. Raman spectroscopy has been demonstrated to be a useful method for the analysis of stress in the graphite and the structure / property relationships both in the relaxed and deformed state. It has been shown that cast iron is not a composite in the normal sense since the presence of the low-modulus carbon reduces the modulus over that of pure iron.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Hirlimann, C., Jouanne, M. and Forrieres, C., "Raman Spectroscopy of Cast Iron", *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy*, **23** (1992) 315.
- [2] Sato, K., "Laser Raman Microprobe Technique; A New Analytical Tool in the Study of Iron and Steel", *Transactions of the Iron and Steel Industry*, **21** (1981) 370.
- [3] Clyne, T.W. and Withers, P.J., "An Introduction to Metal Matrix Composites", Cambridge University Press, (1993).
- [4] Hashin, Z., "A Variational Approach to the Theory of the Elastic Behaviour of Multiphase Materials", *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **29** (1963) 127.
- [5] Wu, T.T., "Effects of Powder Particle Shape on Elastic Properties of Sintered Alloys", *International Journal of Powder Metallurgy*, **1** (1965) 8.
- [6] Rossi, R.C., "Prediction of the Elastic Moduli of Composites", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, **51** (1968) 433.
- [7] Halpin, J.C. and Tsai, S.W., "Environmental Factors in Composite Design", Air Force Materials Laboratory, AFML - TR **67** (1967) 423.
- [8] Elliott, R., *Cast Iron Technology*, Butterworths, (1988).
- [9] Nemanich, R.J. and Solin, S.A., "Observation of an Anomolously Sharp Feature in the Second Order Raman Spectroscopy of Graphite", *Solid State Communications*, **23** (1977) 417.
- [10] Nemanich, R.J. and Solin, S.A., "First and Second Order Raman Scattering from Infinite sizes crystals of Graphite" *Physical Review B*, **20** (1979) 392.
- [11] Young, R.J., "Monitoring Deformation Processes in High Performance Fibres Using Raman Spectroscopy", *Journal of the Textile Institute*, **86** (1995) 360.
- [12] Askeland, D.R., "The Science and Engineering of Materials", PWS Publishing Company, (1994).
- [13] Speich, G.R., Schwoeble, A.J. and Kapadia, B.M., "Elastic Moduli of Gray and Nodular Cast Iron", *ASME Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **47** (1980) 821.